

European Standardization Organizations

The role of research for standardization

WEBINAR Insights from the European Standardization Panel Survey

Making standards for Europe

International

Regional (European)

National

CEN-CENELEC Involvement in ESPS

- ▶ The CEN and CENELEC Presidential Committee made recommendations to the draft survey
- ▶ Promotion of the survey towards CEN and CENELEC Members and network
- ▶ Participation in the workshop to discuss preliminary results
- ▶ Recommendations in the final report align well with CEN and CENELEC Strategy 2030 Goals

► Strategy 2030

 Goal 1: EU and EFTA recognize and use the strategic value of the European standardization system

 Goal 2: Our customers and stakeholders benefit from state-of-the-art digital solutions

 Goal 3: Increase the use and awareness of CEN and CENELEC deliverables

 Goal 4: The CEN and CENELEC system to be the preferred choice for standardization in Europe

 Goal 5: Strengthen our leadership and ambition at the international level

► European strategy

 Chapter 1: Leveraging the European standardization system – to deliver the twin green & digital transition & support the resilience of the single market

 Chapter 2: Upholding the integrity, inclusiveness and accessibility of the European standardization system

 Chapter 3: Global standards-setting: supporting the EU's leading position as a forerunner in key technologies and promoting EU core values

 Chapter 5: Ensuring future standardization expertise – the need for education and skills

Tools for research community

Project Liaison is the formal mechanism that allows a research project to collaborate with an existing Technical Committee (TC) active in the same field.

CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA) is a pre-standardization deliverable designed to meet an immediate need (R&I results) that can be used as a fast-track to future standardization activities

Raising awareness toward the R&I community

- ➔ The EC Code of Practice on Standardization is an important tool for recognizing the role of standardization in valorizing new knowledge

Raising awareness toward standardization community

- ➔ Raising awareness about the importance of linking with R&I community toward CEN and CENELEC technical bodies

Educating a future generation of standards makers

- ➔ As part of [EDU4Standards](#) project, 15 **Academic Standards Days** events will be organized all around Europe in the next 3 years bringing together the academic community and standardization professionals.

Recognizing researchers' contributions

- ▶ Award scheme in place since 2019
- ▶ 4 categories:
 1. Individual researcher/innovator
 2. Research project
 3. Young Researcher
 4. Technical Body Officer
- ▶ Nominations presented by CEN and CENELEC national members
- ▶ Call for nomination open until 30 June 2024!

Recognizing researchers' contributions

- ▶ *Short-term action:* making available online the bibliographies of CEN and CENELEC standards that include a reference to one or more scientific publications, to allow researchers to prove when their scientific contributions have been instrumental for the development of a European standard.
- ▶ *Long-term action:* influencing assessment schemes of universities and research organizations to ensure that that contribution to standardization is recognized as part of the range of activities that maximize the societal and economic impact of research.

ESPS recommendations & CEN-CENELEC approach

Target group

Standard development organisations

Recommendations are well aligned with our goals to ensure standardization system is fit for purpose offering solutions attractive to research community

Industry

We support increasing awareness within companies of the benefits of participating in standardization, particularly focusing on research-active SMEs

Higher education institutes (HEI) and public research organizations (PRO)

We want to raise awareness about standardization in HEI and PRO and encourage them to develop appropriate KPIs

Research Funding Organisations

We support expanding the financial support for standardization as a means of exploitation of research results

Innovation policy

Interesting new avenues to be explored such as encouraging Member States having a research tax credit system to expand the tax base to standardization expenditures

More information

Standards and Research & Innovation

Click on any topic below or use the menu above to jump to any chapter

www.standardsplusinnovation.eu

www.standardspluselearning.eu/

Research@cencenelec.eu

Thank you!

Livia MIAN

LMian@cencenelec.eu

www.cencenelec.eu

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